

Smart Decision Support for Hybrid Hydropower Plants with PV and Hydrogen

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Abstract—This paper examines the hybridization of hydroelectric plants with hydrogen production systems to improve renewable energy integration and grid flexibility. Two scenarios are explored: a small-scale micro-hydro plant and a larger seasonal hydroelectric station, both combined with photovoltaic and hydrogen storage technologies. Through simulations using TRNSYS, the performance of these hybrid systems is evaluated under real-time market conditions. Results indicate that larger hydroelectric plants yield higher revenues and energy output, particularly when integrated with hydrogen storage, which enhances system flexibility and stability. This hybridization approach presents a promising solution for maximizing renewable energy usage and contributing to decarbonization goals.

Keywords— *Smart Decision Support; Hydropower; Hybridization; Optimisation; Smart grids*

INTRODUCTION

Electricity market operators increasingly demand flexibility from market agents to implement strategies in non-conventional market offerings. In the context of Smart Grids, hybrid systems provide the necessary control to balance loads. Specifically, hydroelectric plants and hydrogen generation and storage systems offer significant value in this paradigm, as they can intelligently manage energy storage—reservoirs for hydroelectric plants and hydrogen tanks—and power injection into the grid. Alongside virtual batteries [16] and other elements at various nodes, these systems form the framework of future energy networks. However, many hydroelectric plants currently operate below their nominal capacity due to hydrological, seasonal, or market regulation factors [19], presenting an opportunity to enhance their performance through hybridization with other renewable sources.

Hybrid systems exploit synergies between different technologies, maximizing resource utilization and mitigating limitations associated with the intermittency of solar and wind power [15]. The hybridization of hydroelectric plants with technologies like floating photovoltaic systems [19], batteries with advanced management systems [2], or hydrogen production systems [25] offers solutions to increase flexibility and stability in the electricity grid [18]. Looking ahead, hydroelectric plants are expected to become central nodes in large-scale hybrid energy systems, particularly in countries with abundant water resources [15].

Green hydrogen production, obtained via water electrolysis using renewable electricity, has emerged as a key energy vector for decarbonizing hard-to-electrify sectors such as transportation and certain industries [23, 8]. Advances in hydrogen production and storage technologies have enhanced its viability as a long-term, large-scale energy storage option [11], allowing it to store surplus renewable generation and release it when demand is high, acting as a buffer in the energy

system. The scientific community and industry are investing heavily in hydrogen as an essential component in the transition to sustainable energy systems, given its versatility and potential for integration across different sectors, making it strategic in achieving carbon neutrality goals.

Recent analyses of hydrogen production projects using hydroelectric energy in countries like Canada, Turkey, and China demonstrate that hydroelectric power offers a competitive solution for green hydrogen generation by enabling the production of both electricity and pure water at the same site [12, 25]. For instance, Turkey has developed a hydroelectric map to identify regions with high potential [1], and in Europe, projects like D-Hydroflex focus on the hybridization of hydroelectric plants to produce hydrogen, which could bring significant economic and technical benefits and support policy formulation to foster growth [4]. Implementing these renewable energy projects requires detailed economic analysis considering investment costs, operational expenses, and expected revenues. This analysis can be conducted using analytical models and dynamic energy simulation software. In this study, TRNSYS will be used to model hydroelectric plants and hydrogen systems, including electrolyzers, storage tanks, and PEM fuel cells [6], enabling simulations under different scenarios to assess system performance in response to variations in demand, operating conditions, and electricity markets.

HYBRIDIZATION

Scenarios

To assess the profitability of hybridizing a hydrogen system with a hydroelectric plant, two distinct scenarios have been considered. In both cases, the photovoltaic system and the hydrogen system remain constant in terms of size and production. The variation lies solely in the technologies of the selected hydroelectric plants. These scenarios represent two very different concepts of hydraulic production: a small-scale micro-hydropower plant and a large, seasonal hydroelectric station.

Small hydroelectric power plant (SCENARIO 1)

The first scenario is based on what could be a micro-hydropower[1] generation plant with a capacity of 35 kW, located in a water treatment facility (ETAP). This relatively novel installation integrates a pump operating as a turbine (PaT), allowing the recovery of energy that is currently dissipated through a pressure reduction valve (PRV) located at the inlet of the ETAP.

Since the water flow is constant and continuous due to the plant's operational nature, this system is expected to provide stable energy generation. This small-sized plant exemplifies how these types of turbines can be implemented in industrial sectors as an added value, optimizing resource use.

Seasonal hydroelectric power plant (SCENARIO 2)

The second scenario involves a 2.1 MW hydroelectric plant of the dam-peak type, with an average annual production of 2 GWh and a reservoir capacity of 102.6 hm³. Located in a dry tropical climate, the plant operates with a Francis turbine [14], handling flows between 0.8 and 4.8 m³/s with a nominal head of 56.5 meters.

This plant is ideal for exploring hybridization solutions due to its seasonal operation; the water released downstream is used for irrigation, an activity that occurs only during certain months of the year. Integration with hydrogen systems allows the plant to take advantage of periods of lower water demand or limitations in power injection into the grid, to store and produce energy.

Parameters and components

Turbine PaT

The first scenario uses a hydraulic pump used as a turbine from a mini-hydropower plant in Castilla y León (Spain). In order to obtain its power-flow generation curve, available data from its operation have been used. The curve describing the power generated by the turbine is defined by the following polynomial:

$$P = 957.417 \cdot Q^2 - 192.166 \cdot Q + 30.213 \quad (2)$$

where P is the power output of the turbine (in kW) and Q is the flow rate (in m³/s). The regression has been performed using a degree 2 polynomial. The degree of this polynomial is well adapted to the behavior of the pump used as a turbine, which has a minimum flow rate of 0.119 m³/s.

Turbine Francis

In the second scenario, a Francis turbine has been considered to obtain electricity in the hydropower plant. The Francis turbine is one of the most widely used turbines in the world, due to its high efficiency at high flow rates [14].

In order to model the behavior of the turbine, the power-flow curve was obtained from data provided by both Confederación Hidrográfica del Guadalquivir [3] and a company that operates hydropower plants in Andalucía (Spain). The method used to obtain the curve was ridge regression, using a degree 10 polynomial. The degree of the polynomial was chosen by comparing using the mean squared error metric the result obtained in the regression with the different degrees of the polynomial. Therefore, the curve obtained is expressed by the following polynomial:

$$P = -0.510 \cdot Q^{10} + 9.761 \cdot Q^9 - 74.752 \cdot Q^8 + 284.478 \cdot Q^7 - 514.055 \cdot Q^6 + 193.680 \cdot Q^5 + 574.329 \cdot Q^4 - 188.815 \cdot Q^3 - 1067.230 \cdot Q^2 + 1036.870 \cdot Q + 1.539 \quad (2)$$

As can be seen, the independent term of the equation is different from 0. This is expected, since the ridge regression, while fitting the actual measured data very well, is not exact. For this reason, we have added an additional rule to the equation so that when the flow rate is 0, the power is also 0. Both the regression methodology and the metrics used have been obtained from scikit-learn, a Python machine learning library [21]. The minimum flow rate of the Francis turbine has been limited to 0.8 m³/s.

Solar

For the sizing of the photovoltaic plant, a generation capacity of 500 kW has been selected, which is typical for a photovoltaic generation plant installed for self-consumption at an industrial facility in Spain [10,20] with an approximate ISBN: 978-618-5765-06-4
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surface area of 4,500 m². This approach aims to represent a typical plant that could be installed by any industry or hydroelectric station on the roof of an industrial building or a small solar farm. In any case, for this study, the production and sale of solar energy should not constitute the primary activity of the industry in the case study.

The following values have been used in the modeling:

Table 8: Technical Specifications of the Photovoltaic Module and System Configuration

Photovoltaic Module Specifications		
Parameter	Value	Unit
Maximum Power	100.3	W
Voltage at Maximum Power Point	17	V
Current at Maximum Power Point	5.9	A
Open-Circuit Voltage	21.6	V
Short-Circuit Current	6.5	A
Module Efficiency	11.27	%
Temperature Coefficient of Voc	-0.079	V/K
Temperature Coefficient of Isc	0.02	A/K
NOCT	40	°C
Number of Cells in Module	36	-
Module Area	0.89	m ²
Tau-Alpha Product for Normal Incidence	0.95	-
Semiconductor Bandgap	1.12	eV
Module Series Resistance	0.3065	Ω
Module Temperature at NOCT	313	K
Ambient Temperature at NOCT	293	K
Insolation at NOCT	800	W/m ²
Installed Photovoltaic Power	500,000	W
Number of Modules in Series	16	-
Number of Modules in Parallel	333	Variable

H2

Electrolyzer System

In our virtual hybrid system, a high-pressure alkaline electrolyzer with a power capacity of 500 kW and a nominal production rate of 243.75 kg/h of H₂ will be modeled. This type of electrolyzer has been selected because, firstly, it is a sufficiently mature and reliable technology [9], capable of producing green hydrogen at relatively high pressures. This is particularly advantageous in systems where the intention is to store the hydrogen produced immediately after the electrolyzer, thereby reducing the operational and energy costs of subsequent compression.

Moreover, dimensionally, it is a medium-sized piece of equipment according to the current technological range, suitable for industrial applications. This size is appropriate as an intermediate point between the two study scenarios: the medium-sized hydroelectric plant (2.1 MW) and the micro-hydropower plant (35 kW), acting as a buffer to take advantage of surplus energy generation.

Table 9: Technical Specifications of the Electrolyzer System

Electrolyzer Specifications		
Parameter	Value	Unit
Electrode Area	0.25	m ²
Number of Cells in Series	21	-
Number of Stacks in Parallel	1	-
Maximum Allowable Current Density	670	mA/cm ²
Maximum Allowable Operating Temperature	80	°C
Minimum Allowable Cell Voltage	1.229	V
Thermal Resistance	0.167	K/W
Lower SOC Limit	0.7	-
Upper SOC Limit	0.9	-
Idling Power	1,000	W
Nominal Power	600,000	W
Idling Constant	5.836×10^{-3}	-
Operating Voltage	2.06	V
Ohmic Constant	138.42	V ²
Electrolyzer Installed Power	500,000	W
Number of Electrolyzer Units	20	-
Hydrogen Production at Nominal Conditions	243.75	kg/h

Hydrogen Storage System

For the hydrogen storage system, a three-stage compressor has been sized to compress the hydrogen, directly at the output of the electrolyzer, into a 5 m³ tank with a maximum pressure of 200 bar. The storage system plays a fundamental role in hydrogen technologies. In our case, it serves as an energy storage solution until the control system decides to produce electricity, releasing the hydrogen into the fuel cell.

Table 10: Technical Specifications of the Hydrogen Storage System (Compressor and Tank)

Compressor Specifications		
Parameter	Value	Unit
Number of Parallel Compressors	1	-
Number of Compressor Stages	3	-
Maximum Pressure	200	bar
Tank Volume (VolTankH ₂)	5	m ³
Molar Weight of Gas	2.016	g/mol
Gas Critical Temperature	-240	°C
Gas Critical Pressure	12.9	bar

PEM Fuel Cell System

The final stage of our hydrogen system is a fuel cell. In our case, we have modeled a proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cell capable of producing 250 kW of electricity. This technology is highly mature and well-supported. Moreover, it offers a rapid response in terms of energy production, making it highly useful in our scenarios, as it would be able to inject energy into the grid [25] during intermittent periods when the selling price is high.

The following are the key characteristics used in the modeling:

Table 11: Technical Specifications of the PEM Fuel Cell System

PEM Fuel Cell Specifications		
Parameter	Value	Unit
Number of Cells in Series	21	-
Number of Stacks in Parallel	1	-
Minimum Cell Voltage	0.7	V
Maximum Current Density	1,629	mA/cm ²
Cell Active Area	441	cm ²
PEM Fuel Cell Installed Power	250,000	W
Number of PEM Units	125	-
Base Power per PEM Unit	2,000	W
Hydrogen Consumption at Nominal Conditions	243.75	kg/h
Maximum PEM Power Output	250,000	W
Minimum PEM Power Output	50,000	W
Total Active Area per PEM Unit	4,872	cm ²
Maximum Current per PEM Unit	79.34	A
Minimum Voltage per PEM Unit	14.7	V
Maximum PEM Power Output	250,000	W
Minimum PEM Power Output	50,000	W
Minimum Cell Voltage	0.7	V

Operational conditions

Electricity market

Our model aims to assess the technological and economic viability and profitability of hybridization. In the latter aspect, it is essential to accurately simulate real market conditions. In our study, and for both scenarios, we will use the SPOT prices in Spain [17], where we will collect hourly prices set in the wholesale energy market in real-time or with very little notice. The fluctuation of these prices will determine our control strategies and the relative operation of our production system.

Grid restrictions

The two scenarios have considered the existence of signals from the grid operator allowing or prohibiting the discharge of electrical power to the main grid. These prohibitions could be caused for different reasons:

excess of available renewable energy, insufficient demand, maintenance operations, etc. During the time the grid injection is prohibited, the system can produce hydrogen that can be converted into electricity in the future. The signal is transmitted hourly by using a binary variable.

In this paper, the grid restriction signals [17] that have been used were obtained from grid operator in Castilla y León (Spain).

Control Rules

The control design methodology is based on the following dynamics. Two price thresholds are set: a stop price of 60€/MWh for the sale of renewable electricity, at which point energy is no longer injected into the grid. At this moment, the energy production is used to produce and store hydrogen,

taking into account the tank capacity and min/max power restrictions. On the other hand, an activation price of 130 €/MWh is established for the PEM fuel cell, at which point the fuel cell is activated, consuming the previously stored hydrogen and generating electricity for direct sale.

Additionally, as explained in subsection 2) *Grid restrictions*, the control rules must ensure that no energy is injected into the grid when the operator imposes any restrictions. Taking all of this into account, the hybrid system operates all its components according to their respective dynamics to ensure the correct operation of each unit, aiming to maximize energy sales.

MODEL

The dynamic simulation tool TRNSYS has been used to model our system. Through this software, models have been created for our three main systems: the solar generation system, the hydraulic generation system with the two turbines used in the two case studies, and the hydrogen system. The control strategy defined, as described in subsection 3) *Control Rules*, is implemented through the different TYPES [24] of the software along with internal control equations. As for the variables and parameters used for the equipment, representative values of the case studies were employed, as compiled in Tables 1, 2, 3, and 4. Additionally, with future work in mind, the model configuration allows for parametric variation of critical design variables, such as hydrogen storage capacity, photovoltaic production capacity, string and array configuration of the solar field, or the number of electrolyzers, among others. This flexibility enables optimization of equipment performance according to different strategies.

The following are the TYPES used in each of the three systems described:

Hydraulic System:

The hydraulic subsystem was modeled using a CALCULATOR (turbine equations) and TYPE 9c (hourly flow data).

Photovoltaic System:

The PV subsystem includes TYPE 15 (weather data processor), TYPE 57 (unit conversion), and TYPE 190c (PV array with MPPT) to process meteorological inputs and simulate array performance with maximum power point tracking.

Hydrogen System:

The hydrogen subsystem was implemented with TYPE 100a (electrolyzer control), TYPE 175b (power conditioning unit), TYPE 160a (alkaline electrolyzer), TYPE 164b (compressed storage), TYPE 167 (compressor), and TYPE 170a (PEM fuel cell). Additional control calculators manage electrolyzer operation and hydrogen demand.

RESULTS

Simulation Results:

Turbine Performance Curve in Scenario 1 (PaT):

This graph shows the behavior of the pump operating as a turbine (PaT) in Scenario 1, based on the equations presented earlier, which are used to model the turbine.

Figure 13: Turbine performance curve scenario 1

Turbine Performance Curve in Scenario 2 (Francis):

This graph details the power curve of the Francis turbine in Scenario 2. The relationship between flow rate and generated power is used to model the complete generation system of the hydroelectric plant as a "black box."

Figure 14: Turbine performance curve scenario 2

Comparison of Energy Sale Revenues in Both Scenarios:

This graph compares the revenues obtained from energy sales in the two scenarios (PaT and Francis). It highlights the influence of SPOT market prices on operational decisions and the profitability of each system, illustrating the economic differences between both hybridization approaches.

Figure 15: Comparison of revenue from energy sales in both scenarios.

Power Generation Curves in Scenario 1 (PaT):

This figure presents the power generation curves in Scenario 1, from both the photovoltaic plant (PV) and the micro-hydropower system (PaT), along with the hydrogen system (PEM). This graph helps to understand the operational dynamics of the micro-hydropower system, its variability, and its interaction with hydrogen storage.

Power Generation Curves in Scenario 2 (Francis):

This graph displays the power curves for Scenario 2, which include hydroelectric generation by the Francis turbine, photovoltaic generation (PV), and the hydrogen system (PEM). The figure illustrates the greater stability in hydraulic power generation due to the larger capacity and size of the plant compared to the first scenario.

Figure 16: Power production curves case 1

Figure 17: Power production curves case 2

Evaluation of Scenarios through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

To evaluate the two scenarios proposed in this study, a series of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been defined. These KPIs will enable the analysis of both the energy performance and the economic viability of each configuration, facilitating a direct comparison between the two case studies. The following section describes how these KPIs will be used in the evaluation:

- **Energy Sold to the Grid:** This KPI measures the total amount of energy that each hybrid system exports to the electrical grid. It will be calculated by summing the energy generated by the hydroelectric plant and the photovoltaic plant, while also accounting for the energy converted into electricity through the PEM fuel cell powered by stored hydrogen. This indicator is crucial for determining the effective contribution of each system to the grid and its ability to utilize available energy resources efficiently.
- **Revenue from Energy Sales:** The economic revenue generated from energy sales will be calculated based on SPOT prices from the electricity market. For each scenario, the impact of price fluctuations throughout the day will be evaluated, optimizing energy dispatch when prices are highest. This KPI will help assess the economic profitability of each system, identifying which of the two scenarios generates higher income over the course of a year and under varying operational conditions.
- **Energy Sold vs. Potentially Generable Energy:** This KPI compares the energy that is effectively sold to the grid with the energy that could have been generated under ideal conditions (considering the maximum capacities of the hydroelectric and photovoltaic systems). It allows for an assessment of the operational efficiency of the system, identifying possible losses or limitations, whether due to technical restrictions, insufficient hydrogen storage, or operational decisions that affect overall performance.

- **Energy Distribution:** This indicator analyzes how the generated energy is distributed among different destinations: sale to the grid, self-consumption, or storage in the form of hydrogen. It will examine the operational decisions that determine whether the generated energy is used directly, stored, or sold depending on market conditions. This KPI will provide insights into how effectively each system manages energy resources to maximize its operational and economic efficiency.

Table 12: KPI COMPILATION

KPI	SCENARIO 1	SCENARIO 2
Energy sold to the grid (MWh)	1,098.78	2,243.17
Revenue from energy sales (K€)	171.68	337.24
Energy sold vs potentially generable energy	85.93%	88.27%
Renewable Energy Distribution - PV/Total Renewable	75%	38%
Renewable Energy Distribution - Hydro/Total Renewable	25%	62%
Energy consumed by electrolyzer / Renewable energy production	14%	9%

CONCLUSIONS

The scale of the hydroelectric plant significantly impacts the economic outcomes of hybridization with hydrogen systems. In Scenario 2, the larger capacity plant notably increases the energy sold and the revenues generated, demonstrating that larger hydroelectric facilities can better leverage the economic benefits of this integration. Both scenarios show high efficiency in the utilization of generated energy, reflecting effective optimization in the management and distribution of available energy resources. Moreover, hybridization facilitates the diversification and complementarity of renewable sources, adapting to the specific characteristics of each plant. In Scenario 1, photovoltaic energy complements the micro-hydropower system, while in Scenario 2, the seasonal hydroelectric plant benefits from the solar contribution, particularly during periods of low hydraulic generation. Hydrogen plays a key role by enabling surplus energy storage and adding flexibility to the system, thereby improving its stability and efficiency. This strategy is applicable across various contexts and scales, from small industrial installations to large energy infrastructures, contributing to environmental and social benefits by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting sustainable development.

As the next steps in this research, a parametric optimization is proposed to determine the optimal sizes of the different technologies involved, considering both capital expenditures (CAPEX) and operational expenditures (OPEX) to maximize energy sales. Additionally, the use of various turbine technologies and types of hydroelectric plants will be explored to evaluate their impact on the efficiency and profitability of the hybridized system. Finally, the implementation of pilot projects is planned to validate the theoretical results obtained and adapt the models to real-world operating conditions.

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